

germanicol acetate⁴ and lupeol⁵ and following the chemical shift theory.

The benzene eluted fractions of the same chromatogram afforded *epi*-friedelinol^{6,7} (III), C₃₀H₅₂O (M⁺ 428), m. p. 268°, [α]_D +19.3° (CHCl₃, c 0.103) as crystalline compound (0.15 g, 0.005%). It showed positive LB colouration reaction for triterpenes and exhibited ν_{\max} (KBr) at 3500 (OH), 2930, 1378 and 1352 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyl). On acetylation it gave *epi*-friedelinyl acetate (V), C₃₂H₅₄O₂ (M⁺ 470), m. p. 285°, [α]_D +33° (CHCl₃, c 0.17). V exhibited ν_{\max} at 1732, 1245 and 978 cm⁻¹ and ¹³C nmr signals⁸ (CDCl₃) at δ 170.7 (C=O), 74.5 (C-3), 60.9 (C-10), 53.1 (C-8), 48.0 (C-4), 42.8 (C-18), 41.6 (C-6), 39.6 (C-14 or C-13), 39.2 (C-22), 38.3 (C-13 or C-14), 37.8 (C-5), 37.0 (C-9), 36.0 (C-16), 35.5 (C-19), 35.3 (C-11), 34.9 (C-29), 32.8 (C-21), 32.3 (C-15 or C-12), 32.1 (C-2), 32.0 (C-28), 31.7 (C-30), 30.5 (C-12 or C-15), 29.9 (C-17), 28.1 (C-20), 21.2 (CH₃CO), 20.0 (C-27), 18.5 (C-26), 18.1 (C-25), 17.6 (C-7), 16.3 (C-1), 15.7 (C-24) and 11.2 (C-23). All these data established IV as *epi*-friedelinol which was further confirmed by its direct comparison (superimposable ir, m. m. p. and co-tlc) with an authentic sample.

The chloroform eluted fractions of the main chromatogram afforded a sterol crystallizing from chloroform-acetone as colourless needles, m.p. 155°. It was found identical with stigmasterol by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p., ir and co-tlc).

The chloroform extract of *E. riparium* on chromatographic resolution over silica gel afforded a triterpene from the benzene eluted fractions crystallizing from chloroform-acetone as needles, m. p. 238-40°. This was identical with taraxasteryl acetate (II) in all respects. Besides taraxasteryl acetate, the same chromatogram afforded taraxasteryl palmitate (I), *epi*-friedelinol (III) and stigmasterol from the petrol, benzene and chloroform eluates, respectively.

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Determination of *N-m-Tolyl-p-Methoxy benzo-hydroxamic Acid* and *N-m-Tolyl-p-Chloro-benzo hydroxamic Acid* in Acetone†

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VARIOUS arylhydroxamic acids have been used for solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination¹⁻⁶ of Nb(V), Ta(V), Ti(IV), Mo(VI), W(VI) etc. *N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxy benzo*hydroxamic acid (TMBHA) and *N-m-tolyl-p-chlorobenzo*hydroxamic acid (TCBHA) have been recently used in our laboratory for solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination⁷⁻¹⁰ of Nb(V) and Ti(IV). In continuation of our earlier work on estimation of oximes^{11,12}, thiocarbamides¹³ and biuret¹⁴ the present paper deals with quantitative estimation of benzo hydroxamic acids by enthalpic, conductometric and potentiometric titrations. Results obtained by different methods have been compared.

Experimental

Reagents: All chemical were of A. R. grade. Acetone was purified and made anhydrous as usual¹⁵. The titrants, tetra-*n*-butyl ammonium hydroxide (TBuNH₄OH), potassium hydroxide in isopropyl alcohol (Alc. KOH) and potassium tertiary butoxide in tertiary butyl alcohol (*tert* BuOK) were prepared and preserved as reported earlier¹⁵. TMBHA (m. p. 112°, Mol. Wt. 256) and TCBHA (m.p. 138°, Mol. Wt. 261) were prepared by coupling ethereal solution of freshly prepared *N-m-tolyl* hydroxyl amine with corresponding acid chloride at 0°. The products were recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40°-60°).

Instruments and procedures: A direct reading potentiometer was used for potentiometric titrations. Calomel electrode, prepared with Hg/HgCl₂

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saturated KCl in methyl alcohol was used as the reference electrode and pure aluminium wire (99.99%; 1 mm diam) was used as an indicator electrode. Small portions of aluminium wire (≈ 2 mm) was cut off by a sharp edge cutter just before each titration.

All titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. Methods for enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric titrations were the same as reported previously for oximes^{1a}, thiocarbamides^{1a} and biuret^{1a}. End points were determined graphically and the results of enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric titrations of benzo-hydroxamic acids were compared.

Results and Discussion

Choice of proper titrant: In order to select the most suitable titrant, three different titrants (T₄NH₄OH, Alc. KOH and *tert* BuOK) were tried by various methods (enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric) and % errors were calculated for each estimation. Comparison of the results shows that Alc. KOH gives the best results in enthalpimetric titrations of TMBHA and TCBHA. Rise in temperature at and after the end point is also quite large (2° to 3°) in case of Alc. KOH (Fig. 1). In conductometric and potentiometric

Fig. 1. Enthalpimetric titrations of benzo-hydroxamic acids. I—TMBHA, II—TCBHA ; titrant—Alc. KOH.

titrations also Alc. KOH is found to give minimum errors (± 2.1 and $\pm 0.5\%$ respectively) and hence it was selected as the most suitable titrant for further investigation.

Effect of concentration of solute: In order to observe the effect of concentration of solute and to know the limits of estimation of benzo-hydroxamic acids, stock solution of TMBHA containing 4.0434 mg/ml of the compound was prepared in acetone. Different volumes (1-20 ml) of this solution were diluted to 20 ml with acetone and 5 ml of each of these solutions were titrated enthalpimetrically with Alc. KOH. 5 ml of each of the solutions were separately diluted to 25 ml and titrated with Alc. KOH conductometrically and potentiometrically. Similar titrations were performed for TCBHA.

Comparison of results shows that smaller weights of TMBHA (1 to 12 mg) can be estimated quantitatively by enthalpimetric titration. Maximum % error in such estimations is $\pm 1.3\%$. For larger quantities of TMBHA (14 to 20 mg), the results obtained are lower, probably because of incomplete reaction. For TCBHA, relatively higher quantities (1 to 16 mg) can be determined by enthalpimetric titrations. This may be due to enhanced acidity of the compound because of the substitution of the methoxy ($-\text{OCH}_3$) group by chloro ($-\text{Cl}$) group.

In conductometric titrations, graphs for conductance vs volume of Alc. KOH did not show a sharp break and end points were determined by extrapolation (Fig. 2). Errors in estimation were

Fig. 2. Conductometric titrations of benzo-hydroxamic acids. I—TMBHA, II—TCBHA ; titrant—Alc. KOH.

also relatively large. Maximum errors for TMBHA and TCBHA were 2.0% and 1.7% respectively. However, conductometric titrations could be used to estimate 1-20 mg of benzo-hydroxamic acids.

Potentiometric titrations were found to give the best results. Graphs for potential vs volume of base show sharp rise in potential at the end point (Fig. 3) and hence it can be determined accurately.

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titrations of benzo-hydroxamic acids. I—TMBHA, II—TCBHA ; titrant—Alc. KOH.

Errors in estimation of both TMBHA and TCBHA are always less than 1.0%. (Maximum errors were $\pm 0.7\%$ and $\pm 0.6\%$ for TMBHA and TCBHA respectively). The method can be used to estimate quantitatively 1-20 mg of benzohydroxamic acids.

Potentiometric titrations give the most accurate results but the method requires longer time. Enthalpimetric titrations are much simpler and quicker than the other methods and give quite satisfactory results. Enthalpimetric titration is therefore recommended for quick estimation of benzohydroxamic acids upto 12 mg in routine work.

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Titrimetric Determination of Ascorbic Acid with Chloramine-T using Oxazine Dyes as Indicators†

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VERY few indicators have been reported for the titrimetric determination of ascorbic acid with chloramine-T and these are starch¹, variamine blue², cacotheline³ and N-substituted phenothiazines⁴. We have now investigated the use of seven

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oxazine dyes, Capri Blue (CB), Solochrome Prune AS (SPAS), Gallamine Blue (GB), Celestine Blue (CLB), Meldola's Blue (MB) (Colour Index Nos. 51015, 51040, 51045, 51050 and 51175 respectively), Cresyl Fast Violet Acetate (CFVA) and Resazurin (RSZ) as indicators in this titrimetric determination in neutral and hydrochloric, acetic and sulphuric acid media. The titrations can be performed satisfactorily in (1) neutral medium employing CB, SPAS, GB, CLB and RSZ, (2) hydrochloric acid medium using CB, SPAS, GB and CLB and (3) acetic acid medium using SPAS, GB and CLB as indicators. The titrations cannot be performed in sulphuric acid medium. The method employing hydrochloric acid as titration medium and CB, SPAS, GB and CLB as indicators can be applied for the determination of ascorbic acid content of commercial pharmaceuticals.

Experimental

Approximately 0.1 N solutions of chloramine-T and ascorbic acid (0.5 g of EDTA per litre was used as stabiliser) were prepared and standardised as per accepted methods. Dye solutions (0.1%) were prepared in deionised water from the following samples: CB (Chroma); SPAS, GB, CLB, MB and CFVA (E. Gurr); RSZ (B. D. H.). Other chemicals were of reagent grade quality.

Procedure: Ascorbic acid solution (4-10 ml of 0.1 N) is treated with sufficient water or 1 : 1 hydrochloric or acetic acid and diluted to 50 ml. 1 ml of 0.1 M potassium bromide and 0.2 ml of 0.1% indicator solution are added and the mixture titrated with the chloramine-T solution. The conditions of the titrations are as follows:

Hydrochloric acid medium: CB: 1.5-4.0 M; SPAS: 0.5-2.5 M; GB: 0.5-1.5 M; CLB: 0.5-2.0 M.

Acetic acid medium: SPAS, GB and CLB: 0.04-1.0 M.

The colour changes at the end points are:

Neutral medium: CB: dark blue to pale blue; SPAS: bluish violet to colourless; GB and CLB: violet to colourless; RSZ: pink to colourless.

Hydrochloric and acetic acid media: CB: Green to colourless; SPAS, GB and CLB: pink to colourless.

The method developed for titration in hydrochloric acid medium can be utilised for the determination of ascorbic acid contents of commercial pharmaceutical preparations as per the procedure described by Rao *et al*⁵.

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